

Influence of Locus of Control and Job Involvement to Organizational Culture Applied by Employees on Bank X

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Abstract—As one of the big government bank, Bank X is paying attention its performance, so that it can compete. One of them is the existence of organizational culture which recognized with term TIPEC (Trust, Integrity, Professionalism, Costumer Focus, and Excellence). In application of organizational culture, it is needed the existence of employee involvement (job involvement). It can be influenced by various factors, such as Locus of Control.

Related to above mentioned, the problems are how employee tendency of Locus of Control, how job involvement, how organizational culture applied by employees and how influence of Locus of Control and job involvement to the organizational culture applied by employees.

Researchers collected data with questioner spreading, and respondents number of 30 people. After that, the data were analyzed with SPSS software constructively. The influence of Locus of Control and job involvement to the application of organizational culture was strong, i.e. 58.3%.

Keywords—organizational culture, bank, employee locus of control, job involvement

I. INTRODUCTION

HUMAN kinds as activator of an organization or company are influenced by many factors. One of these is locus of control concept, which developed by Rotter [9]. It is ensured to give contribution to quality of performance on an individual person, i.e. an initial response as basic of further responses. Locus of control itself is divided in two, i.e. locus of control that to orient internally and externally.

Job Involvement according to Robins [10] is people attitude that take sides psychologically to job, and consider the job is the most important in his/her life. Both factors, Locus of control and Job involvement, are variables that used in measurement or understand how employee application of organizational culture at a company. Organizational culture according to Mangkunegara [2] is value, regulation, norm those applied at a company as rule of employee behavior in job.

In banking, especially Bank X became object of research,

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and the organizational culture has been established, as called 'TIPEC' (Trust, Integrity, Professionalism, Excellent, and Consumer focus). This is the attitude to competition in banking in very competitive, in order to be more capable to various challenges. Based on the organizational culture, the employees have rules in the job.

So far, the employees of Bank X have understood the organizational culture. However, it is not fully applied yet. One aspect is how TIPEC organizational culture application by employee in their selves due to influence of internal or external locus of control.

The objectives of research were to understand how Locus of Control of employees at Bank X, Job Involvement of employees at Bank X, the organizational culture applied by employees at Bank X, influence of Locus of Control to the organizational culture applied by employees, influence of Job Involvement to the organizational culture applied by employees, and to understand the influence of Locus of Control and Job Involvement to the organizational culture applied by employees at Bank X.

II. RESEARCH AND ANALYSIS METHODOLOGY

In this research, it was used population of employees at Bank X as number of 30 people. Site research was carried out directly at the company as the object of research and the data were obtained with interview. The interview was a dialogue with involved people at the company, and then to be directed to certain problem with some prepared questions. Besides that, it used question inquiry, as called questionnaire, i.e. the data collection with giving written questions, and the results would be analyzed for understanding how far the influence of Locus of control and Job involvement to organizational culture applied by employees.

The researched variables were Locus of Control and Job Involvement as independent variables (X), whereas organizational culture applied by employees was as dependent variable (Y). Locus of Control was independent variable (X1), i.e. the concept was developed by Rotter, as give contribution to quality of performance of one individual. Locus of control consist of internal and external orientations, as dimension for this variable, with inside indicator of motivation, skill, knowledge, opportunity, partners and fate. The used instrument was Rotter [9], and has been tested the validity by

Brownel [6].

Job involvement was independent variable (X2), according to Robbins [7], it was employee involvement where an individual attitude take side psychologically to the job, and the job is most important. According to Kanungo [8], there are 3 dimentions; employee participation, consistency and inciator motivation. The used instrumentation was by Jeaffey & Weatherholt [3]. This instrument measures job involvement thought 5 points of likert scale, with very agree (5) and very not agree (1). This instrument is job involvent sizes that very reliable, and usually used in many research by Aranya [9], Morrow & Wirth [10].

Based on Rotter scale, an examination was carried out for giving score one (1) on every external statement and score zero (0) for every internal statement. The score values between 0 (most internal) and 7 (most external). It was established a criteria based on median as; 0-3: tendency to locus of internal control and 4-7: tendency to locus of external control.

Based on Likert scale, it was analyzed every answer of questionnaires, and furthermore it was calculated the frequency and percentage. It was determined the scale or weighing of every alternative answer, that given score of 5-4-3-2-1. The best score was five (5), and the worst score was one (1). It was taken pair of researched data, that the number **n** respondents, so that

$$Y_{i-n} = (X1_{i-n}, X2_{i-n}) \quad (1)$$

where X1=Locus of control, X2=Job involvement, Y=organizational culture applied by employees. After the data were collected, it was analyzed by multiple regressions.

Data transformation from ordinal to interval was to fulfill a part of requirement of parametric analysis or using regression analysis. It was used MSI (Method of Successive Interval) transformation.

We used double linear regression to analyze an influence two variables, dependent with independent variables [11]. The equation is:

$$\hat{Y} = a + b_1 X_1 + b_2 X_2 \quad (2)$$

where Y= dependent variable of organizational culture applied by employees, X1=Locus Of Control, X2=Job Involvement, a=constant, and b1, b2 = regression coefficients.

For hypothesis test, it was used statistically test as

$$F_{cal} = \frac{JK_{reg}/k}{JK_{res}/(n-(k+1))} \quad (3)$$

where JK_{reg}= double correlation coefficient, JK_{res}= sum of total square minus regression square, k=sum of independent variables, n=sum of samples, with refuse H0 if F_{cal} > F_{table}, so Ha is accepted (significant). Accepted H0 if F_{cal} < F_{table}, so Ha is refused (not significant).

The double correlation analysis was used to understand a degree of strength the relations among variables of X1 (locus of control), X2 (job involvement), and Y (organizational culture applied by employees). The formula of double

correlation is:

$$r^2 = \frac{JK_{(reg)}}{\sum Y^2} \quad (4)$$

where r²=double correlation coefficient, JK(reg)=sum of square, $\sum Y^2$ = sum of total correlation squares.

Based on correlation coefficient (r), so that r values between -1 < r < 1, described as follows.

If r=1, there is a linear relation among X1, X2, and Y variables perfectly positive. If r=-1, there is a linear relation among X1, X2, and Y variables perfectly negative. If r on -1<r<1, the correlations are not perfect.

Determination coefficient analysis is used to know percentage (%) of influence magnitude of variable X1 (locus of control) and X2 (job involvement) to Y (organizational culture applied by employees), with the formula:

$$KD = r^2 \times 100\% \quad (5)$$

where, KD= coefficient of determination, r²=square of double correlation.

III. RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The data of research were a number of scores those obtained from answers of responses or statements for three research variables, i.e. variables of Locus of Control (X1), Job Involvement (X2), organizational culture applied by employees (Y).

A validity indicates how far the relevance of question to what asked or measured in a research, a question can be said valid and can measure a research variable, if coefficient of validity ≥ 0.3. Table 1 shows the recapitulation of validity-reliability.

TABLE I THE RECAPITULATION OF VALIDITY-RELIABILITY

Variables	Item	Coefficient of Validity	Critical Points	Remarks	Coefficient of Reliability	Critical Points	Remarks
Job Involvement (X2)	Pert_1	0.813	0.3	Valid	0.705	0.7	Reliable
	Pert_2	0.574	0.3	Valid			
	Pert_3	0.688	0.3	Valid			
	Pert_4	0.680	0.3	Valid			
	Pert_5	0.734	0.3	Valid			
	Pert_6	0.866	0.3	Valid			
	Pert_7	0.863	0.3	Valid			
Organizational Culture (Y)	P1	0.846	0.3	Valid	0.716	0.7	Reliable
	P2	0.769	0.3	Valid			
	P3	1.000	0.3	Valid			
	P4	0.880	0.3	Valid			
	P5	0.851	0.3	Valid			
	P6	0.909	0.3	Valid			
	P7	0.952	0.3	Valid			
	P8	0.735	0.3	Valid			
	P9	0.705	0.3	Valid			
	P10	0.530	0.3	Valid			
	P11	0.722	0.3	Valid			
	P12	1.000	0.3	Valid			

Based on Table 1, the result of 19 questionnaires to respondents has fulfilled the requirements of validity (0.3) and reliable (0.7).

TABLE II RESPONDENT RESPONSES ABOUT LOCUS OF CONTROL

No	Locus of Control	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1	Internal	9	30
2	External	21	70
Total		30	100

Table 2 describes about locus of control. Based on the table, from 30 respondents, only 21 respondents (70%) were on external category, whereas the remains 9 respondents (30%) were on internal category. This case identified that most research respondents were on external category. External Locus of Control, according to Penner is when a people consider what happen on his/her life is originated from outside (environments, opportunity, fate). An individual that has Internal Locus of Control, has more of positive aspect, compared to that has External Locus of Control. However, this did not mean the employee of Bank X not have positive aspects. On site, the performance was influenced by external environmental factors, such as place of job, opportunity of leadership role to communicate well to the employees.

In this case, it was described respondent responses regarding Job Involvement, that was consists of employee participation dimension, consistency and motivation. Table 3 shows the respondent responses regarding the employee participation.

TABLE III RESPONDENT RESPONSES ABOUT EMPLOYEE PARTICIPATION

No	Questions	Respondent Answers										Total	
		Very agree		Agree		Uncertain		Not agree		Very not agree		F	Score
		F	Score	F	Score	F	Score	F	Score	F	Score	F	Score
1	Always involved in every office activity	11	55	12	48	4	12	3	6	0	0	30	121
2	Obey the rules is the form of awareness in myself	17	85	13	52	0	0	0	0	0	0	30	137
3	In a work, the employees have to have initiative in order to be effective	13	65	15	60	2	6	0	0	0	0	30	131

Based on continuum line, the opinion and attitude of respondents to respondent involvement in every office activity was indicated by the score as 121. If this number is transformed based on score interpretation, so that it is obtained as $121/150 \times 100\% = 80.67\%$. This number if described in the continuum line was on high category. Based on the interview, it was also obtained the data those most of employees at Bank X are always involved in office activity, such as every three months, the section heads do coaching to performance of employees, and all employees attend.

Based on continuum line, the opinion and attitude of respondents to obey the rules were awareness form in my self, indicated by the score as 137. If this is transformed based on score interpretation criterion, so that obtained $137/150 \times 100\% = 91.33\%$. Such number was described in continuum line was on very high category. Based on the interview, usually the employees of Bank X have had awareness of office rules, such as in a day every employee registers twice, in the morning and afternoon.

Based on continuum line respondent opinion and attitude to employee job has to have initiative in order to the job do more

effectively indicated by a score as 131. Furthermore, that number was transformed based on the score interpretation criterion, so it was obtained $131/150 \times 100\% = 87.33\%$. This number was described in a continuum line, which on very high category. According to the interview of majority of employees, they admitted frequently to do initiative in office activity, such as on establishment of employee performance in a beginning of year, if there was not something suitable, it had to be discussed to a head section.

TABLE IV RESPONDENT RESPONSE REGARDING CONSISTENCY

No	Questions	Respondent Answers										Total	
		Very agree		Agree		Uncertain		Not agree		Very not agree		F	Score
		F	Score	F	Score	F	Score	F	Score	F	Score	F	Score
4	Application of office rule became responsible of company and as need of employees	10	50	18	72	2	6	0	0	0	0	30	128
5	Policy that valid consistent, need by company	17	85	11	44	2	6	0	0	0	0	30	135

Based on the continuum line, the respondent opinion and attitude to the office rule application became company responsible and need for all employees, indicated by the score as 128. If this number was transformed based on the score interpretation criterion, so that it was obtained $128/150 \times 100\% = 85.33\%$. This number, if described in continuum line, was on very high category. In site, the employees admitted that the office rule was company responsible, such as leave twice a year.

Based on the continuum line, the respondent opinion and attitude to the valid consistent policy was very need by the company, indicated by the score as 135. If this number was transformed based on the score interpretation criterion, it was obtained as $135/150 \times 100\% = 90\%$. This number, if described in continuum line, was on very high category. Based on the interview of majority of employees, they admitted the consistent policy, so that the performance could conduct well, such as an establishment of work target on every employee in a year.

TABLE V RESPONDENT RESPONSE REGARDING MOTIVATION

No	Questions	Respondent Answers										Total	
		Very agree		Agree		Uncertain		Not agree		Very not agree		F	Score
		F	Score	F	Score	F	Score	F	Score	F	Score	F	Score
6	Always effort to develop career to obtain greater power	10	50	13	52	6	18	1	2	0	0	30	122
7	Work hard in order to obtain better career	10	50	16	64	2	6	2	4	0	0	30	124

Based on the continuum line, the respondent opinion and attitude to the always effort to develop career to obtain greater power was indicated by score as 122. If this number was transformed based on the score interpretation criterion, so that it was obtained $122/150 \times 100\% = 81.33\%$. This number, if described in continuum line, was on between very high and high categories. Like as admission of employees, they reached a performance in order to obtain job promotion.

Based on the continuum line, the respondent opinion and attitude to work hard to obtain better career was indicated by

score as 124. If this number was transformed based on the score interpretation criterion, so that it was obtained $124/150 \times 100\% = 82.67\%$. This number, if described in continuum line, was on very high category. Like as admission of employees, they worked hard in order to obtain assessment of work well, and further to influence their career.

After authors analyzed the results in detail, Table 6 below shows the description of respondent answers in average to Job Involvement on Bank X.

TABLE VI STANDARD OF AVERAGE VALUES OF RESPONDENT ANSWERS REGARDING JOB INVOLVEMENT

Average values	Job Involvement	Average values of respondent answers
1.00 – 1.80	Very low	
1.81 – 2.60	Low	
2.61 – 3.40	Medium	
3.41 – 4.20	High	
4.20 – 5.00	Very high	4.28

Based on Table 6, the average value, obtained from 30 respondents was 4.28, indicated classification level of Job Involvement, included in very high category. Thus, it was concluded that generally the Job Involvement in Bank X has been on very high category. This indicated that the performance of Bank X was determined by involvement of employees in the work dominantly, such as how far the employees worked to reach the established work.

TABLE VII RESPONDENT RESPONSES REGARDING INNOVATION AND RISK DECISION

No	Questions	Respondent Answers										Total	
		Very agree		Agree		Uncertain		Not agree		Very not agree		F	Score
		F	Score	F	Score	F	Score	F	Score	F	Score		
1	In work, I always has the attitude of creative and innovative	10	50	15	60	5	15	0	0	0	0	30	125
2	I can take decision fast and well	6	30	20	80	4	12	0	0	0	0	30	122

Based on the continuum line, the respondent opinion and attitude to work always be creative and innovative, indicated by score as 125. This was transformed to base on score interpretation criterion as $125/150 \times 100\% = 83.33\%$. This value was described on continuum line as very high category. This was also supported by the employees that had a capable to use IT for supporting the job or work.

Based on the continuum line, the respondent opinion and attitude to always take a decision fast and well, indicated by the score as 122. This was transformed to base on score interpretation criterion as $122/150 \times 100\% = 81.33\%$. This value was described on continuum line as high category. Based on the interview, the employees admitted always to able take a decision fast and well, such as a Teller when was happened a problem in save transaction, she could look for solution fast.

TABLE VIII RESPONDENT RESPONSE REGARDING ATTENTION TO BE DETAIL

No	Questions	Respondent Answers										Total	
		Very agree		Agree		Uncertain		Not agree		Very not agree		F	Score
		F	Score	F	Score	F	Score	F	Score	F	Score		
3	Always give priority carefulness in work	9	45	18	72	3	9	0	0	0	0	30	126

Based on the continuum line, the respondent opinion and attitude to always gave priority accuracy in work, indicated by a score as 126. This was transformed to base on score interpretation criterion as $126/150 \times 100\% = 84\%$. This value was described on continuum line as very high category. Based on the interview, especially on Tellers, they paid attention on the accuracy, due to a part of examination on the work.

TABLE IX RESPONDENT RESPONSES REGARDING ORIENTATION OF RESULTS

No	Questions	Respondent Answers										Total	
		Very agree		Agree		Uncertain		Not agree		Very not agree		F	Score
		F	Score	F	Score	F	Score	F	Score	F	Score		
4	Always able to reach a target of funding as a determined establishment of company	4	20	7	28	19	57	0	0	0	0	30	105
5	Always able to reach a target of company	3	15	14	56	13	39	0	0	0	0	30	110

Based on the continuum line, the respondent opinion and attitude to reach target of funding as company establishment indicated with score as 105. This was transformed to base on score interpretation criterion as $105/150 \times 100\% = 70\%$. This value was described on continuum line as high category. The employees of customer service admitted to always able to reach a target through client recruitment.

Based on the continuum line, the respondent opinion and attitude to reach company target was indicated by score as 110. This was transformed to base on score interpretation criterion as $110/150 \times 100\% = 73.33\%$. This value was described on continuum line as high category. Basically, according to employees, when evaluation on an ending of year, they always reached the company target, although it was not 100% exactly.

TABLE X RESPONDENT RESPONSES REGARDING ORIENTATION OF PEOPLE

No	Questions	Respondent Answers										Total	
		Very agree		Agree		Uncertain		Not agree		Very not agree		F	Score
		F	Score	F	Score	F	Score	F	Score	F	Score		
6	Always given opportunity by place of work to be creative	13	65	16	64	0	0	1	2	0	0	30	131
7	Always ready to be up against risk in job	7	35	20	80	0	0	2	4	1	1	30	120

Based on the continuum line, the respondent opinion and attitude to always given opportunity by company to be creative indicated by score as 131. This was transformed to base on score interpretation criterion as $131/150 \times 100\% = 87.33\%$. This value was described on continuum line as high category. Some employees admitted to be given opportunity to be creative when they worked, such as how behaviors when they serviced clients in order to be satisfy (Teller, Customer

Service).

Based on the continuum line, the respondent opinion and attitude to always ready to face all risks in the jobs was indicated by the score as 120. This was transformed to base on score interpretation criterion as $120/150 \times 100\% = 80\%$. This value was described on continuum line as high category. According to the interview results, almost employees admitted, ready to face any risk, such as whether reach or not a target of job.

TABLE XI RESPONDENT RESPONSES REGARDING TEAM ORIENTATION

No	Questions	Respondent Answers										Total	
		Very agree		Agree		Uncertain		Not agree		Very not agree		F	Score
		F	Score	F	Score	F	Score	F	Score	F	Score		
8	In establishment of policy, it was always based on agreement together	10	50	18	72	0	0	2	4	0	0	30	126
9	Applied policy was suitable importance of individual and group.	1	5	18	72	8	24	3	6	0	0	30	107

Based on the continuum line, the respondent opinion and attitude to establish office policy always base on agreement together was indicated by the score as 126. This was transformed to base on score interpretation criterion as $126/150 \times 100\% = 84\%$. This value was described on continuum line between high and very high categories. Based on the interview results, this was indicated by an establishment of job on early year where head section would socialize to the employees, whether be agreed or not.

Based on the continuum line, the respondent opinion and attitude to applied policy in the office suitable with importance of individual and group, was indicated by score as 107. This was transformed to base on score interpretation criterion as $107/150 \times 100\% = 71.33\%$. This value was described on high category of continuum line. Based on the interview results, this was indicated by the establishment of employee performance in early year, where the head section would socialize, and then whether be agreed of not by the employees.

TABLE XII RESPONDENT RESPONSE REGARDING AGGRESSIVENESS

No	Questions	Respondent Answers										Total	
		Very agree		Agree		Uncertain		Not agree		Very not agree		F	Score
		F	Score	F	Score	F	Score	F	Score	F	Score		
10	The office demanded employees to have high initiative	4	20	22	88	4	12	0	0	0	0	30	120
11	Have enough skill to be competitive	6	30	18	72	6	18	0	0	0	0	30	120

Based on the continuum line, the respondent opinion and attitude to the employees to have high initiative was indicated by the score as 120. This was transformed to base on score interpretation criterion as $120/150 \times 100\% = 80\%$. This value was described on between high and very high categories. Based on the interview results, this was indicated by employee initiative when propose an objection to the head section. Based on the continuum line, the respondent opinion and attitude to enough skill to be competitive was indicated by the score as 120. This was transformed to base on score interpretation criterion as $120/150 \times 100\% = 80\%$. This value

was described on between high and very high categories. Based on the interview results, this was indicated by an achievement of employee performance, so that they could collect more number of clients, compared to other Bank.

TABLE XIII RESPONDENT RESPONSE REGARDING STABILIZATION

No	Questions	Respondent Answers										Total	
		Very agree		Agree		Uncertain		Not agree		Very not agree		F	Score
		F	Score	F	Score	F	Score	F	Score	F	Score		
12	Feel in an environment of conducive work	8	40	17	68	5	15	0	0	0	0	30	123

Based on the continuum line, the respondent opinion and attitude to feel on a conducive environment of work was indicated by the score as 123. This was transformed to base on score interpretation criterion as $123/150 \times 100\% = 82\%$. This value was described on high category. Based on the interview results, it was indicated that the employees would be comfortable.

After authors analyzed the results in detail, Table 14 below describes the respondent answers in average to organizational culture applied by employees at Bank X.

TABLE XIV AVERAGE VALUE STANDARDS OF RESPONDENT ANSWER OF ORGANIZATIONAL CULTURE APPLICATION

Average values	Organizational culture	Average values of Respondent Answers
1.00 – 1.80	Very low	
1.81 – 2.60	Low	
2.61 – 3.40	Medium	
3.41 – 4.20	High	3.99
4.20 – 5.00	Very high	

Based on table 14 above, the obtained average value of 30 respondents was 3.99, indicate classification level of employees apply organizational culture as high category. Thus, it was concluded generally the organizational culture applied by employees at Bank X has been on high category. This was also supported the statement by the head section when interview progress. One of indications was the increasing of performance every year.

To see how far the influence of Locus of Control (X_1) and Job Involvement (X_2) to application of organizational culture applied by employees at Bank X, it was used double regression model. To be easy on calculation, it was included all independent variables (predictors) for analysis. Thus, it is obtained the equation of double regression as follows.

$$\hat{Y} = 14.666 + 7.934 X_1 + 0.550 X_2 \quad (6)$$

The values of regression coefficient on independent variables described if one independent variable rose as one unit, and another independent variable was constant or closed to zero practically, so that the bonded variable value was approximated to increase or decrease suitable with the sign of regression coefficient of independent variables.

From the double linear regression equation above, it was the constant value as 14.666. This mean, if the organizational

culture applied by employees was influenced by both independent variables, locus of control (X_1) and job involvement (X_2) were zero, so that the average value of application organizational culture would be 14.666.

The sign of regression coefficient of independent variables indicated arrow of relation from the corresponding variables to the dependent variable. The value of regression coefficient for independent variable X_1 (locus of control) was positive, indicated an existence of relation as same direction between locus of control and the organizational culture applied by employees. The meaned of regression coefficient of locus of control variable as 7.934 was for every increasing of locus of control of one unit, it caused increasing of the organizational culture applied by employees as 7.934.

The regression coefficient of independent variable X_2 (job involvement) was positive, indicated the existence of relation as same direction between job involvement and the organizational culture applied by employees. The regression coefficient of job involvement variable as 0.550 contained meaning for every increasing of one unit of the organizational culture applied by employees, it caused the increasing of the organizational culture applied by employees as 0.550.

The double correlation was used to understand how closeness between locus of control and job involvement to the organizational culture applied by employees. Based on the obtained table result, it was obtained the correlation coefficient value (R) as 0.764. This correlation coefficient was positive sign, that meaned there was strong relation between locus of control and job involvement to the organizational culture applied by employees.

To understand how much the influence was given by locus of control and job involvement to the organizational culture applied by employees, so that it was used coefficient of determination with the formula as follows.

$$\begin{aligned}
 KD &= r^2 \times 100\% \\
 &= (0.764)^2 \times 100\% \\
 &= 58.3\%
 \end{aligned}$$

Based on the calculation result above, it was obtained coefficient value of determination as 58.3%. This meaned the organizational culture applied by employees would be influenced by locus of control and job involvement as 58.3%. Based on partial determination of each independent variable to dependent variable can seen on Table 15.

TABLE XV THE PARTIAL INFLUENCE OF X_1 AND X_2 TO Y

Variable	Standardized coefficients	Zero order	Partial influence (%)
X_1	0.680	0.659	44.8 %
X_2	0.387	0.350	13.6 %
Total			58.3 %

Based on Table 15, it is indicated that independent variables has most influence to the organizational culture applied by employees was locus of control (X_1), i.e. 44.8%. Whereas, job involvement (X_2) gave the influence of the organizational

culture applied by employees was of 13.6%. Based on this research, locus of control and job involvement could influence to the organizational culture applied by employees simultaneously. Nevertheless, the most influence variable was locus of control.

IV. CONCLUSION

Based on the research results, the analysis and supporting theory, most Locus of Control employee at Bank X was on external category, with the number of respondents of 21 or 70% of population. Job Involvement on Bank X has been on very high category, indicated by average value of 4.28. The organizational culture applied by employees on Bank X has been on high category, indicated by the average value as 3.99. Locus of Control had the influence of 44.8% to the organizational culture applied by employees. Job Involvement had the influence as amount of 13.6% to the organizational culture applied by employees. Locus of Control and Job Involvement had the influence as amount of 58.3% to the organizational culture applied by employees.

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